

1 **A relationship between p53 and Braf in mammalian cells.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the primary tumor from mice with tumors arising from p53 null status or
8 from genetically engineered mice whose tumors contain a dominant negative p53 mutation to discover
9 cancer cell dependencies associated with p53 status. When comparing total transcription, the Braf
10 transforming kinase encoded by *BRAF* was among those genes whose expression whose most tightly
11 regulated between cells with p53 KO (knock-out) and mutant p53 genetic status. Braf functioned through
12 interactions with the mitogen-activated protein kinase MAPK8, oncogene ETV3 and the T-complex
13 homeobox *Tcp11l2*. BRAF thus appears to be an oncogenic cancer cell dependency in p53-deficient
14 contexts.
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